

Population dynamics of green leafhopper with respect to time and space

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The behavior of rice green leafhopper populations with respect to time and space was studied by catching and counting leafhoppers with light traps at

different locations in 1976–77 and 1977–78. The Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR), New Delhi, provided financial support for the work.

The light traps were fitted with 100-watt electric bulbs and installed near the plant virus experimental field at Kalyani, at the model farm of the W. Bengal Directorate of Agriculture at Habra, and at the Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, ICAR, at Canning.

The lights were turned on each evening and off the next morning. The relative occurrence of *Nephotettix virescens* and *N. nigropictus*, and the male-to-female ratio of each were recorded. A calendar of the characteristics of the populations was prepared (see table).

The distribution patterns of the green leafhoppers were similar in different years and sites, but more critical analysis showed that they differed in a few characters (see table). □

Calendar of the population distribution of the green leafhopper in three locations in West Bengal, India, in a 2-year period.

Observation	Kalyani		Habra		Canning	
	1976–77	1977–78	1976–77	1977–78	1976–77	1977–78
First appearance	1st wk, Apr.	1st wk, Apr.		2d wk, Apr.		April
Disappearance	1st wk, Dec.	2d wk, Dec.	3d wk, Feb.	2d wk, Dec.	2d wk, Feb.	2d wk, Feb.
Appearance of high population	3d wk, Sept. to 3d wk, Nov.	3d wk, Sept. to 4th wk, Oct.	Oct. to Nov.	2d wk, Sept. to 2d, wk, Oct.	1st wk, Oct. to 2d wk, Oct.	Apr. to 2d wk, May
Peak populations	4th wk, Sept. to 3d wk, June	4th wk, Sept.	1st wk, Nov.	3d wk, Sept.	2d wk, Oct. to 1st wk, Jan.	1st wk, Jan. to 2d wk, Dec.

Biology of the green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens*

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The biology of the green leafhopper *N. virescens* was studied from April 1977 to March 1978 in a glasshouse. Male and female adults were collected from rearing chambers and released in cages of TN1 seedlings. Eggs were collected from the seedlings and again placed on caged 25-day-old TN1 seedlings. The seedlings were observed and the moultings recorded every 24 hours.

During the report period, *N. virescens* completed 11 generations. The figure shows the time required to complete each generation.

Hatching occurred within 5 to 9 days of incubation in the 1st, 2d, 3d, 4th, 5th, 7th, 8th, and 9th generations. The incubation period was only 3 to 5 days in the 6th generation, but was 9 to 12 days in the 11th.

The biology of *Nephotettix virescens* in the glass house, April 1977–March 1978.